

ORGANIZATIONAL CRISIS SITUATIONS RESOLVED THROUGH THE MEDIA

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Abstract

In case of crisis situations, organizations' connections with the press play a salutary role. Complex and complicated, this relationship involves the activation of numerous levers that build a necessary communication with the mass media. The dimensions of our approach did not allow us to highlight all the aspects on which such a link is built, but we have drawn only some general frameworks, important to follow, in case organizations face moments of crisis.

Keywords: communication, crisis, mass media.

1. THE ROLE OF MANAGEMENT IN CRISIS SITUATIONS

Organizational crisis situations represent testing moments for the life of any organizational structure and the management team has here to maintain and properly conduct communication with journalists, to transmit information about facing the crisis, about evaluating its effects, about restoring the organization. The tools that help build the organization's relationship with the press are the release, the conference and the press file. The crisis communication must be concise, with a brief but accurate exposition of the events, with a specification of the measures taken by the organization to mitigate the effects of the crisis. In turn, the press conference will be prepared by knowing the positions supported in front of the journalists, by emphasizing the role of the spokesperson. Much richer is the press file, one of the most important ways of relating to the mass media. The clarity of the relationship leads, with certainty, to the efficiency of the measures taken to combat the crisis. The press remains a necessary means of rapid communication between the organization and its audiences.

Eliminating a crisis situation requires the organization to be aware of, coordinate and control emerging emergencies, by rethinking some measures, prepared in time. Effective crisis management leads the organization to the ability to maximize its chances and to reduce the damage caused by the new situation in which it finds itself. Communication is certainly one such measure.

Besides this, we believe, the relationship with the press is one of the elements that can help an organization overcome the moment of crisis. An important measure, which must be taken immediately, consists in appointing a spokesperson, chosen from among credible people, able to understand the aspects of the crisis, its implications, as well as the solutions that can help the organization to overcome these moments.

The person designated as spokesperson will set an official point of view and will maintain a permanent link with the press. Therefore, he must possess thorough knowledge and have the necessary skills for effective communication with journalists. This becomes all the more important as the media can play a decisive role in overcoming crisis situations in the life of an organization. Often, the media crisis joins the real crisis, amplifying it. There have been situations where fluctuations in the leadership of organizations, panic, excessive justification or counterattack have damaged the relationship with the press and caused a series of reactions that are harmful to the organization. Of course, we are not talking here about the need to develop a relationship of submission to the media, but about maintaining a climate of mutual support. Because, when the organization sees the presentation of the facts to the press as a threat and, consequently, hides the information, then the materials about the crisis are distorted, and the public believes that the organization's resources to deal with the crisis are much reduced. The fear that the disclosure of data will damage the image of the organization actually guarantees the continuous and detailed publication of information about the crisis long after it has ended, as well as the abundance of sensational data, and this because the press will turn to outside sources, which often give rise to rumors and speculation" (Newsom D. et alii, 2003, p. 362).

2. MEANS OF PRESS RELATIONS: THE PRESS RELEASE, THE PRESS CONFERENCE AND THE PRESS FILE

The role of the media in mitigating the effects of the crisis that devastates an organization is all the more important since, it is known, people know most of the events through those exposed in newspapers, on radio or television. That is why it is necessary that the information, related to a special situation experienced by the organizations in crisis situations, be correctly done, not to amplify the state of affairs, to help the public opinion to bring its contribution, where appropriate, to solving some manifestations of the crisis. Because the communication problems of an organization faced with a moment of crisis aim at four particular aspects: the internal communication of the respective organization, communication with its audiences, communication with the actors of the crisis and communication with the press.

Related to this last type of communication, it is important that the organization is the first to contact the press, so it must write and send a *press release* immediately. Its role is to inform journalists about the situation created and about the measures that have already been applied. The release must be concise, one page, must include a description of the event, how the organization acknowledges its mistakes that led to the outbreak of the crisis, the name of the person at the head of the team managing the crisis, and the manner in which it is expected that the organization problem will be solved. After the release of the first press release, others will follow over time, as the public must be informed about the evolution or involution of the crisis situation, about the constant efforts made by the organization to remove or, at least, to limit the extent of the crisis.

Once the state of the organization is made public, journalists will search for more and more information, document themselves, analyze similar situations that happened in other organizations, reveal the manner in which they overcame difficult moments. The interest of the media will be all the greater, the more serious the consequences of the crisis: we are referring here to the loss of human lives, to the production of major material damages, to disturbed social, economic or cultural systems, to the involvement of some personalities in the crisis. It creates, therefore, a need for direct, urgent communication between the mass media and the organization, which translates, most of the time, through the organization of a *press conference*.

This becomes an effective means of informing journalists, through which questions are answered, clarifications are given, even some attacks from the media are countered. It is important that, in the event that organizations hold a press conference, their representatives should be prepared, know in depth the actual situation of the institution, and answer honestly the media's questions, some of them even uncomfortable. The crisis team will know the positions, the information, the attitudes, the strategies that will be revealed to the journalists, and the spokesperson will become the most important person in this duel of questions and answers. Numerous situations are commented on in the specialized literature, in which the spokespersons of some institutions were subjected to simulations similar to crises, precisely because of the need to successfully face meetings with the press.

The third stage, followed by an organization in crisis during the period of contact with the mass media, is represented by *the press file*. Of all the communication means between organizations and journalists, the press file is certainly the most important, as it provides essential data about the organization, its history, traditions, values, personalities. Also, here appears a

list of the members of the crisis team, those who make up the core of the fight against the difficult situation the organization is going through.

The formation of a *press file* requires a long time, that is why public relations specialists prepare it from the period of normality, initially sketching the general lines, then assembling them into an efficient and complete document. Of course, when the crisis starts, new, updated information will be added to the information already existing in a press file, absolutely necessary for the mass media to know the actual situation in which the organization is.

CONCLUSIONS

Moments of crisis demand correct, quick, concrete, effective measures, therefore, in the relationship with the press, public relations specialists must adopt the best attitude, namely transparency. This presupposes a total openness to the information needs of the public and to those who help in this knowledge process, with the help of the journalist. The organization's contact with the press is permanent, because the data transmitted is based on efficiency, speed and correctness. Thus, specialists from the public relations department of the organization are recommended to know in detail the measures imposed by the crisis period, to summon the press, even to build a nucleus that will help journalists receive the necessary information. The image of the organization, as it must be perceived by the mass media, will be one of solidarity, of exact knowledge of the factual situation, of possessing all the information communicated to the press, so that their repetition does not occur.

Regardless of the form in which the relationship with journalists is carried out - through press release, press conference, press file or even face to face - it must be approached calmly, without pressure from one side or the other. The clarity of the relationship leads, with certainty, to the efficiency of the measures taken to combat the crisis. The press remains a necessary means of rapid communication between the organization and its audiences.

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